

BUSINESS ANALYSIS OF PADDY PROCESSING UNIT: A CASE STUDY OF SHRI GANESH AGRO INDUSTRY, ARJUNI MORGHAON, GONDIA

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Abstract

The Research Project titled "Business Appraisal of Paddy Processing Unit: A Case Study of Shri Ganesh Agro Industry, Arjuni Morgaon, Dist. Gondia" presents a comprehensive business analysis of paddy processing unit, with a specific focus on the case study of Shri Ganesh Agro Industry, Arjuni Morgaon a paddy processing unit established in 1957 by Mr. Jayprakash Bhaiyya in Arjuni Morgaon, Gondia, Maharashtra. The study aims to estimate the fixed capital investment, cost and return, workout the BEP and identify the constraints faced by Shri Ganesh Agro Industry. The Fixed Capital Investment of Shri Ganesh Agro Industry is Rs. 111.646 lakhs, Fixed Cost of Shri Ganesh Agro Industry is Rs. 21.36423, Variable Cost of Shri Ganesh Agro Industry is Rs. 2025.64816 lakhs, Break Even Point of Shri Ganesh Agro Industry is Rs. 0.05099 lakhs, Benefit Cost Ratio is 1:1.12 and major Constraint observed in Shri Ganesh Agro Industry is Repair and Maintenance of Machineries.

Keywords: Paddy processing, Fixed Cost, Variable cost, Constraints, Industry

Introduction

The rice mill industry in India is a pivotal part of the nation's agricultural economy, marked by a diverse range of small to large-scale mills. Despite significant technological advancements, many mills still operate with outdated equipment, although modernization efforts are underway, focusing on automation and efficiency. Government support through various schemes and subsidies is helping to upgrade infrastructure and facilitate better access to finance. The industry is also placing increasing importance on enhancing rice quality to meet international standards, crucial for maintaining and expanding export markets.

Gondia is Rice producing district. The district predominantly has tribal population. Over 30 per cent of its area is under forest cover and 40 per cent area under agriculture. Practically the entire agricultural population is either directly or indirectly dependent on the success of this crop. The district is one of the highest Rice producing districts in the state. Making rice for domestic consumption is the main use of India Rice Milling. In India, rice is a staple grain that is eaten in a variety of ways, such as boiled or steamed, and as an ingredient in many regional cuisines. The rice milling industry produces a range of rice varieties, including parboiled, non-basmati, and basmati rice, to meet the varied needs of consumers.

The present project is selected to find the Profitability of the Rice Mill, At Arjuni morgaon in Gondia District. Shri Ganesh Agro Industry (Rice Milling Industry) is running from Eighteen years. It was established in 10 November 1957. Jay Prakash Bhaiyya Sir, owner of Shri Ganesh Agro Industry and Mr. Bhagwan Joshi Sir is the Manager of the industry. They sells our processed Rice in other States i.e. MP, AP, with packaging and the product name.

The specific objectives of the study are:

1. To estimate the fixed capital investment of Shri Ganesh Agro Industry.
2. To estimate cost and return of Shri Ganesh Agro Industry.
3. To workout the BEP of Shri Ganesh Agro Industry.
4. To identify the constraints faced by Shri Ganesh Agro Industry.

Hypothesis of the study are:

- a) Past literature suggest that, the Rice Processing firms are profitable venture. Therefore, it is hypothesed that the Shri Ganesh Agro Industry is profitable in Rice Processing.
- b) Considering the reviews, it is hypothesed that the Shri Ganesh Agro Industry is facing major constraint repair and maintenance of machineries in the Rice Processing unit.

Materials and Methods

The methodology of this study employs a case study design to comprehensively analyze the capital investment, fixed cost, variable cost

and gross returns of Shri Ganesh Agro Industry, a paddy processing unit in Arjuni Morgaon, Gondia. Conducted over the fiscal year 2023-2024, the research combines qualitative methods, including interviews, observations, and document analysis, with quantitative techniques like surveys and production data analysis. Primary data was collected through direct interactions with the unit's owner, staff, and associated labourers. Analytical tools such as cost and returns analysis, breakeven point analysis, and Benefit cost ratio assessments were used to evaluate the economic viability and marketing efficiency of the unit. The study also identifies key challenges faced by the owner, such as repairing and maintenance of machineries, shut down of electricity, low quality of Rice, losses during milling and difficulties in skilled labour availability factors affecting the sustainability and profitability of paddy processing.

Result and Discussion

I. Fixed Capital Investment of Selected Paddy Processing Unit Installed processing capacity of Shri Ganesh Agro Industry

Table no. 1 states that, installed processing capacity was 480 qtl/day and actual number of working days was 278 in 12 hours per day and actual processing capacity utilized was 240 qtl /day.

Purchasing of Raw Material (2023-24)

Table No. 2 states that, purchasing of raw material in the year 2023-2024 was in the month of November and December. Highest purchase quantity in the month of November was 42,280 qtl and lowest purchase quantity in the month of December was 24,440 qtl. Total purchase quantity was 66,720 qtl.

Capacity Utilization of Shri Ganesh Agro Industry

Table No. 3 states that, capacity of Shri Ganesh Agro Industry was 240 qtl/ day. Number of working days was 28 days in the selected year. Quantity of Rice actually milled in Rice mill was 30,024 qtl which is obtained from 45% of 66,720 qtl raw paddy.

The fixed capital investment of Shri Ganesh Agro Industry

From the above table no. 4 it is revealed that the 1.88 and 16.12 per cent of the capital investment was in building and land followed by machinery which constitute in Shri Ganesh Agro Industry was calculated in 55.26 per cent. The other investments is made on vehicles, Furniture, electrification and investment formed a more or less similar percent contribution Shri Ganesh Agro Industry.

Overall the Land, Machinery, Building and Vehicle are major cost contributing in total fixed cost investment respectively.

II. Cost and Return of Shri Ganesh Agro Industry

Table No. 5 states that, while the total fixed cost was Rs. 21.36423 per annum of Shri Ganesh Rice Mill. Fixed cost per quintal was Rs. 0.00033.

Table No. 6 states that, while the total variable cost was Rs. 2025.64816 per annum of Rice Mill. Purchase of raw material formed major part i.e. 98.81. Average variable cost per year for Shri Ganesh Agro Industry revealed that casual labour charges formed 0.43 per cent share in total variable cost. It showed that casual labour charges Rs. 8.856. Repair and maintenance charges is Rs. 4 lakhs. Total variable cost is Rs.2025.64816 and total variable cost per quintal is Rs. 0.03036 of Shree Ganesh Agro Industry.

Table No. 7 states that, Gross Return procured in Shri Ganesh Agro Industry was 66,720 qtl in the selected year and Total Gross Return per quintal is Rs. 2305.176.

Table No. 8 states that, the relative economic efficiency of the Rice Mill could be judged in terms of break-even quantities. Therefore, an attempt was made to estimate Break - Even Point for Shri Ganesh Agro Industry, Arjuni Morgaon. The Break - Even quantity of Rice processing is the one at which total revenue equalizes total cost for average Rice Mill. The results on this behalf are presented in Table . It is observed from the table that the Rice Mill Break - Even quantity of Rice was less than the actual quantity handled by Rice Mill.

III. Breakeven Point of Shri Ganesh Agro Industry.

Table No. 9 states that, the relative economic efficiency of the Rice Mill could be judged in terms of break-even quantities. Therefore, an attempt was made to estimate Break - Even Point for Shri Ganesh Agro Industry, Arjuni Morgaon. The Break - Even quantity of Rice processing is the one at which total revenue equalizes total cost for average Rice Mill.

The results on this behalf are presented in Table . It is observed from the table that the Rice Mill Break - Even quantity of Rice was less than the actual quantity handled by Rice Mill. The Break-Even quantity of Paddy was 0.05099 quintal of the actual quantity milled by this Mill.

Overall, the Break-Even Point of Shri Ganesh Agro Industry was Rs. 0.05099 which is total revenue equalizes total cost of average of Rice Mill.

IV. Constraints faced by Shri Ganesh Agro Industry

Major constraints faced by companies from India is low productivity. But there are also so many barriers faced by company. The major problems faced by the Rice Milling units included interruption in power supply, difficulties in labour availability, packaging material, high costs of Paddy procurement, high cost of working capital and repairs and maintenance. The problems were ranked based on industry's owner. As depicted from Table No.15 that, the most important constraints faced by Shri Ganesh Agro Industry is repairing and maintenance of machineries, 2nd shut down of electricity, 3rd low quality of Rice, 4th losses during the milling, and 5th difficulty in skilled labour availability. In the research some of the problems are listed as per the rating.

These above mentioned are some constraints faced by Shri Ganesh Agro Industry, Arjuni Morgaon. But the company always tries to overcome this barriers.

Conclusions

Fixed Capital Investment of Shri Ganesh Agro Industry for the selected year 2023-2024 was Rs. 111.646, The total Fixed Cost was Rs. 21.36423 per annum of Shri Ganesh Agro Industry and Fixed cost per quintal was Rs. 0.00033, Total Variable cost was Rs. 2025.64816 and total variable cost per quintal was Rs. 0.03036 of Shree Ganesh Agro Industry, Total Gross Return per quintal was Rs. 2305.176, The Benefit Cost ratio was 1:1.12, The Breakeven Point of Shri Ganesh Agro Industry was 0.05099 qtl and The major constraints faced by Shri Ganesh Agro Industry is repairing and maintenance of machineries.

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Table No. 1 Installed processing capacity of Shri Ganesh Agro Industry

Sr. No.	Particulars	
1	Size of unit	Small
2	Number of working days	278
3	Installed processing capacity (qtl./day)	480
4	Actual Processing capacity utilized (qtl./day)	240

Table No. 2 Purchasing of Raw Material (2023-2024)

Sr. No.	Month	Purchase Quantity (Qtl)
1	January	-
2	February	-
3	March	-
4	April	-
5	May	-
6	June	-
7	July	-
8	August	-
9	September	-
10	October	-
11	November	42,280
12	December	24,440
	Total	66,720

Table No. 3 Capacity Utilization of Shri Ganesh Agro Industry

Sr. No.	Particulars	Quantity	%
1	Capacity of Rice Mill (qtl/day)	240	-
2	Number of working days	278	-
3	Quantity processed (qtl)	66,720	-
4	Quantity of Rice actually milled (qtl)	30,024	-
Quantity of main product obtained (qtl)			
1	Main Product	30,024	45
Quantity of breakdown obtained (qtl)			
1	Broken Rice	12,010	18
2	Rice Bran	4670.4	7
3	Husk	16,680	25
4	Rejected Rice	3336	3
	Total	66,720	100

Table No. 4 Fixed capital investment of Shri Ganesh Agro Industry

Sr. No.	Item	Purchased Price / Construction Price (Rs.)	Total Amt. (Rs.) In lakhs	% Share
1	Acquisition of land	2,10,000	2.1	1.88
2	Water supply structure	30,000	0.47	0.42
	a. Bore-well			
	b. Pipe line	17,000		
3	Construction of building	10,00,000	18	16.12
	a. Building and civil work			
	b. Godowns	8,00,000		
4	Machinery and Equipments		61.7	55.26
	a. Paddy Cleaner	4,50,000		
	b. De-stoner	2,50,000		
	c. Husker cum Rubber roller	4,00,000		
	d. Seperator	3,00,000		
	e. Polisher	6,00,000		
	f. Silky Polisher	4,00,000		

Table No. 5 Fixed cost of Shri Ganesh Agro Industry Per Annum

Sr. No	Item	Depreciation	Interest on fixed capital	Principle of EMI	Total (Rs.) in lakhs	% Share
1	Water supply structure	2115	4700	2350	0.09165	0.42
2	Building	64800	1,80,000	72,000	3.168	14.82
3	Machinery and Equipment	277650	6,17,000	308500	12.031	56.31
4	Furniture and Fixtures	5400	15,000	6,000	0.264	1.23
5	Computer	2475	2,200	2750	0.07425	0.34
6	Printer	4320	2,400	4800	0.1152	0.53
7	Laptop	3038	2700	3375	0.09113	0.42
8	AC	1395	3100	1550	0.06045	0.28
9	Fan	1350	1500	1500	0.04350	0.20
10	Fire Extinguisher	495	660	550	0.01705	0.07
11	Licence	10800	1200	12000	0.24	1.12
12	Vehicles	119250	265000	132500	5.1675	24.18
	Total fixed cost				21.36423	100
	Fixed cost per quintal				0.00033	

Table No. 6 Variable Cost of Shri Ganesh Agro Industry Per Annum

Sr. No.	Item	Qty	Cost per unit (Rs.)	Per Annum value (Rs.) in lakhs	% Share
1	Permanent / Monthly paid				
	a. Manager	1	15,000	1.8	0.08
	c. Accountant	1	10,000	1.44	0.07
	c. Watchman	1	5000	0.6	0.02
2	Casual / Daily paid			8.856	0.43
3	Purchase of raw material	66,720	3,000	2001.6	98.81
4	Packaging and labelling	10,008	27	0.27216	0.01
5	Repair and maintenance of building and machineries			4	0.19
6	Electricity Charges	12	30,000	4.5	0.22
7	Postage, Telephone and Stationary	12	1,500	0.18	0.008
8	Fuel Charges	12	20,000	2.4	0.11
	Total			2025.64816	100
	Variable cost per qtl			0.03036	

Table No. 7 Gross Return of Shri Ganesh Agro Industry

Sr. No.	Item	Rate per quintal (Rs.)	Quantity (qtl.)	Value (Rs.) in lakhs
1	Head Rice	5500	30,024	1651.32
2	Broken Rice	3500	12,010	420.336
3	Rejected Rice	2000	3336	66.72
4	Rice Bran	2500	4670.4	116.76
5	Husk	300	16,680	50.04
	Total		66,720	2305.176

Table No. 8 Economics of Shri Ganesh Agro Industry

Sr. No.	Particulars	Quantity (Qtl)	Price per (Qtl)	Total (Rs.)
A) Main Product				
1	Rice	30,024	5500	1651.32
B) Brekdown of paddy				
2	Broken Rice	12010	3500	420.336
3	Bran	4670.4	2500	116.76
4	Husk	16,680	300	50.04
5	Rejected Rice	3336	2000	66.72
C)	Gross Returns			2305.176
D)	Total cost			2047.01239
E)	Net Return			258.16361
F)	Benefit Cost Ratio			1:1.12

Table No. 9 Break-Even Point of Shri Ganesh Agro Industry

Sr. No.	Particulars	Values (Rs.) in lakhs
1	Fixed Cost	21.36423
2	Variable Cost	2025.64816
3	Total Cost	2047.01239
4	Gross Returns	2305.176
5	Net Return	258.16361
6	Fixed Cost per quintal	0.00033
7	Variable Cost per quintal	0.03036
10	Break - Even Point (Qtl)	0.05099
11	B:C Ratio	1:1.12

Table No. 10 Constraints faced by Shri Ganesh Agro Industry

Sr. No.	Constraints	Rank
1	Reparing and Maintenance of Machineries	I
2	Shut down of electricity	II
3	Low quality of Rice	III
4	losses during the milling	IV
5	Difficulties in skilled labour availability	V